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Asset-like characteristics of perennial crops and on farm trees in small holder agrifood systems

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Small-scale subsistence farming produces a significant portion of the global food supply and can support relatively high population densities. However, chronic food insecurity on small farms persists as poverty traps when socio-ecological and techno-cultural drivers reinforce negative outcomes for individuals and households. This paper explores the asset-like characteristics of perennial crops and on-farm trees within these smallholder agrifood systems. Ultra-poverty associated with chronic hunger is geographically concentrated among African farmers living on small, resource-limited plots of land. Yet, food and farming systems exist that have sustainably supported relatively high population densities over long periods, occurring within the wide agricultural diversity of the world's 500 million small farms but remain poorly characterized. They risk being eroded due to global agricultural homogenization, meaning the window of opportunity to learn from traditional agrisystems is narrowing.

By examining various case studies and empirical data, the research highlights how perennial crops and trees function as critical assets, providing long-term productivity, resilience against climatic variability, and contributions to soil health. Autochthonous approaches to intensification may partially explain the bifurcation of successful small farms from those falling into policy-resistant poverty traps. We recommend the inclusion and potential formalization of a wider range of green assets, such as trees and tree-like perennials, in research on sustainable rural livelihoods and food and nutrition security

This paper defines 'household green assets' as privately managed stores of living biomass that accrue value over time and yield a single net return larger than any prior flow of services or benefits. Valuable green assets are characterized by asynchronous or flexible harvest timings, allowing rapid liquidation to support food security and related livelihood outcomes in response to unforeseen negative events or excessive stress. Secondary products or services from maturing green assets may provide additional minor flows of value, such as the medicinal uses of enset. These living stores of biomass often require years to mature into a 'current' asset whose full value can be readily accessed.

Green assets represent a distinct class of natural assets within the 'natural capital' framework. Unlike commonly governed natural capital assets, green assets are privately held and valued for their eventual net return rather than continuous service flows. This distinguishes them from agroforestry trees, which primarily provide environmental services to enhance primary crop yields, and silvopasture trees, which primarily provide livestock fodder.

We identify two main classes of green assets: those contributing to food security and those contributing to livelihoods in general. Timber trees, often managed in plantations or as 'trees on farm', exemplify livelihood assets. Livestock may be categorized as both livelihood and food security assets. Few edible crops fit exclusively into the food security category, with enset being a notable example due to its unique management. Other examples include sago palm, cultivated for its starchy stem, and certain palms and agave species harvested for non-food purposes.

We propose that harvest flexibility is a key attribute of valuable green assets on small farms, allowing them to function like economic assets within a financial system. This flexibility helps stabilize food system production and address seasonal food insecurity, thereby enhancing the resilience of smallholder agrifood systems.